

ISic1354

I.Sicily inscription 1354

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐνθάδε κείται Εὐ
2. τυχιανὸς ζήσας ἐν
3. Χ(ριστῶ) τελευτᾷ τῆ πρ(ὸ) θ
4. καλανδῶν Αὐγους
5. τῶν ὑπ(ατείᾳ) Ἀνικίου Αὐχενί
6. ου Βάσσου κα(ὶ) Φλ(αυ)ί(ου) Φ(ι)λίππου

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491454

EDCS 39101734

PHI 140858

PHI 175602

PHI 331400

Bibliography

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